

1-Year Hospital-Based Study to Assess the Effect of Visual Stimuli on Heart Rate Variability in Middle Aged Males

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract

Aim: The aim of the present study was to test the effect of visual stimuli on HRV in middle aged male.

Methods: The present 1-year study was conducted in the Department of Physiology, Patna Medical College and Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India for one year. Healthy 100 males of middle age group of 40-60 years were included in the study.

Results: This study signifies that closing eyes for a while might help heart by increasing the parasympathetic component of the cardiac autonomic activity and the parasympathetic component of the cardiac autonomic activity increased during the closed eye condition when compared to the open eye condition. The mean value of HF nu for under CEC was significantly greater (<0.05 level) when compared to OEC. The values of LF nu and LF/HF under CEC appear to be smaller than those OEC.

Conclusion: When compared to the open eye condition, when the eyes are closed state of the eyes. Closing your eyes for a few moments could benefit your heart by enhancing the parasympathetic component of cardiac autonomic activity.

Keywords: Autonomic activity, Heart Rate Variability, visual stimuli

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Introduction

Physiological responses to environmental stimuli have been investigated intensly. [1,2] Heart rate at rest is regulated through the activity of cardiac autonomic nervous system. The stimulation in the sympathetic nervous system increases heart rate and excitation of parasympathetic nervous system reduces heart rate by increasing vagal tone. Heart Rate Variability (HRV) is a specific and sensitive non-invasive tool to evaluate cardiac autonomic activity. HRV is the degree of variation of the heart rate under the balanced influence of sympathetic and parasympathetic

components of the cardiac autonomic nervous system. HRV also indicates the extent of neuronal damage to autonomic nervous system. Human beings are very sensitive to light exposure, and changes of light intensity can shift many physiological parameters like melatonin, alertness, body temperature, heart rate (HR), and heart rate variability (HRV). [3,4]

The HRV describes the complex variation of beat-to-beat intervals mainly controlled by the autonomic nervous system (ANS) through the interplay of sympathetic and parasympathetic neural activity at the sinus

node. [5] In healthy subjects, typically showing a pronounced inter individual HRV [6], the dynamic cardiovascular control system is characterized by its ability to adapt to physiologic perturbations and changing conditions maintaining the cardiovascular homeostasis. [7]

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Heart rate at rest is regulated through the activity of cardiac autonomic nervous system. HRV is the degree of variation of the heart rate under the balanced influence of sympathetic and parasympathetic components of the cardiac autonomic nervous system. Heart Rate Variability (HRV) is a specific and sensitive non-invasive tool to evaluate cardiac autonomic activity. HRV also indicates the extent of neuronal damage to autonomic nervous system. The aim of the present study was to test the effect of visual stimuli on HRV in middle aged male.

Table 1: Basic characteristics of subjects

Variables	Subjects
Age in years	46.24±1.60
BMI (kg/m ²)	25.65±0.50

Table 2: Comparison of FFT spectrum between CEC and OEC

HRV	CEC	OEC	p-value
LF nu	30.700±3.97	34.280±4.950	<0.05
HF nu	70.630±6.620	68.270±4.720	<0.05
LF/HF	0.580±0.07	0.670±0.08	<0.05

Methods

The present 1-year study was conducted in the Department of Physiology, Patna Medical College and Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India for one year. Healthy 100 males of middle age group of 40-60 years were included in the study.

Inclusion and exclusion criteria

Subjects who were obese or with history of diabetes mellitus, hypertension, respiratory illness, cardiac diseases and endocrinal disorders were excluded. Subjects on any medications were also excluded.

The effects of visual stimuli on cardiac autonomic activity using HRV was studied in 100 healthy middle-aged males. Beat to beat R-R intervals were continuously recorded under closed eye condition and the open eye condition. HRV frequency domain parameters like LF nu, HF nu, LF/HF were obtained with the help of RMS polyrite-D version3.0.11.

Statistical analysis

Analysis of variance (ANOVA) has been used to find the significance of study parameters between three or more groups of patients, Student t test (two tailed, independent) has been used to find the significance of study parameters on continuous scale between two groups Inter group analysis. Significance is assessed at 5% level of significance.

Results

This study signifies that closing eyes for a while might help heart by increasing the parasympathetic component of the cardiac autonomic activity and the parasympathetic component of the cardiac autonomic activity increased during the closed eye condition when compared to the open eye condition. The mean value of HF nu for under CEC was significantly greater (<0.05 level) when compared to OEC. The values of LF nu and LF/HF under CEC appear to be smaller than those OEC.

Discussion

During the last few decades, particularly following the publication of the guidelines on heart rate variability (HRV), the importance of HRV as a tool for assessing the autonomic nervous system activity in many different diseases and conditions has steadily increased. [9]

Snieder et al. [10] found in 196 male and 210 female middle-aged twins that oral contraceptive use and menopausal status had no effect on HRV. However, Moodithaya et al. [11] concluded that both aging and declined estrogen levels are associated with the autonomic alterations that are seen among postmenopausal women.

As reported by Voss A et al [12], directly comparing the values of frequency domain indices from various studies is quite difficult due to the different calculation modes (such as fast Fourier transform vs. autoregressive methods, different window functions, partly spectral corrections and others) and due to the units of the result values (e.g. ms^2 , natural or common logarithm). Litscher D et al. [3] indicated that changes in the activity of parasympathetic nervous system can alter heart rate much more rapidly exerting beat-by-beat control of heart rate compared to sympathetic nervous system. LF-HF ratio is sensitive measure of sympathovagal balance. C. Cajochen et al. showed that increase in LF-HF ratio indicates increased

sympathetic activity and decrease in ratio indicates increased parasympathetic activity. HFnu is an index of parasympathetic activity. [8]

T. Rechlin et al. [13] showed that changes in automaticity of the pacemaker caused by increased activity of pacemaker caused by increased activity of parasympathetic nerves are rapid due to quick activation of special acetylcholine-regulated K^+ channels in the cardiac cells and Decay of the cardiac response is quick due to rapid hydrolyzation of acetyl choline.

N. E. Rosenthal et al in their studies indicated that participants who were exposed to red light (versus a control color) exhibited a decrease in HF-HRV, and this result was associated with worse cognitive performance. Strength and limitations of the study- The present study was focused only at the effect of visual stimuli on the cardiac autonomic frequency domain parameters. The study is limited to one geographical area and confined to one gender of a specific age group. [14,15]

Conclusion

When compared to the open eye condition, when the eyes are closed state of the eyes. Closing your eyes for a few moments could benefit your heart by enhancing the parasympathetic component of cardiac autonomic activity. The cardiac autonomic activity component increased. The parasympathetic component of the cardiac autonomic activity increased during the closed eye condition when compared to the open eye condition.

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